

Acetoacetarylamides as Chelating Ligands, Part V. Uranyl Chelates[†]

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Uranyl acetoacetarylamides have been synthesised in pure crystalline forms by the reaction of methanolic solutions of uranylacetate with acetoacetarylamides (viz. acetoacetanilide, acetoacet-orthochloroanilide, acetoacet-anisidide and acetoacet-o-toluidide). These are red to orange in colour. The visible and ultraviolet spectra of solutions of uranyl acetoacetarylamides in ethanol are presented. Infra-red spectra has been utilised as a diagnostic tool for characterisation of these complexes. The electrolytic conductance measurements in aqueous solution at 30°C indicate that the solutions are rapidly hydrolysed with the deposition of $\text{UO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. But conductance measurements in freshly prepared methanol solution indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The complexes are all weakly diamagnetic and are seven co-ordinated.

This study is a part of a comprehensive programme on chelating behaviour of acetoacetarylamides towards metallic elements. In five earlier papers¹⁻⁴ lengthy reports have appeared on the oxovanadium (IV) complexes, iron (III) complexes and on the adduct formation of copper (II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) acetoacetarylamides with aromatic heterocyclic nitrogenous bases. It was observed that the chelating properties of these ligands are quite comparable to acetylacetone. This communication describes the uranyl chelates of acetoacetarylamides (viz. acetoacetanilide, acetoacet-orthochloroanilide, acetoacet-anisidide and aceto-acet-o-toluidide).

Transitional elements of Group IV, V and VI are found to form mononuclear oxocations of the type MO^{+n} and MO_2^{+n} . The most extensively studied, best characterised and most stable oxo-metal entities are the dioxo-uranium(VI)^{5,6} and oxo-vanadium(IV)⁷ ions. The strongly bound oxygens of these oxo-metal entities remain intact during chemical reactions and thus present additional means for studying the complexes of the oxo-cations beyond those normally available with transition metal complexes. The formation of multiple covalent bonds to oxygen by uranium has been explained theoretically⁵. The tendency of oxygen to delocalise its $p\pi$ electrons away from its highly compact valence shell by forming π bonds with π electron acceptor metals probably explains the formation of metal oxygen bond at least qualitatively. Our interest in the fascinating coordination chemistry of oxo-metal cations is revealed in a number of publications^{1,8-10}. The mononuclear

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dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes with acetoacetarylarnides and benzoylacetanilides will be described in a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ligands, acetoacetanilide, acetoacet-ortho-chloroanilide, acetoacet-anisidide and acetoacet-o-toluidide were of L.R. grade and were purchased from B D H (England). Uranylacetate dihydrate and methanol were of B.D.H., A.R. variety.

Uranium analysis was made by igniting the complex to 800-850°C for several hours and weighing the residual U_3O_8 . Nitrogen was determined by Duma's semimicro combustion technique. The conductance measurements were carried out using a Philip's Conductivity Bridge and a dip type cell. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done in a Gouy Balance at room temperature (304°K) with solid specimens. Electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in ethanol solution were taken in a Hilger-Watts Uvispeck Spectrophotometer using one cm. cells. The relevant analytical, conductance and spectral data are recorded in the Table.

TABLE I

Analysis, Colour, Melting point, Molar conductance and Electronic spectra of Uranyl complexes†

Compound	Colour	M.P.* °C	Molar con- ductance in methanol mhos	Analytical results			Electronic spectra		
				%U	%N	%H ₂ O**	Wave number cm ⁻¹	ε	
1. [UO ₂ (Ace-anil) ₂] HAcc-anil	Dark red	167	20	Found: 30.0	5.4	—	37,000	17,500†	
				Reqd: 29.8	5.2		28,170	1750	
2. [UO ₂ (Ace-Cl-anil) ₂] HAcc-Cl-anil	Orange needles	208	22	Found: 26.6	4.4	—	22,200 sh	340	
				Reqd: 26.4	4.6		29,610 w.sh	75	
							37,040	17,000†	
							28,170	1800	
3. [UO ₂ (Ace-anis) ₂] HAcc-anis. 2H ₂ O	Orange	150	22	Found: 26.1	4.4	4.1	22,220 sh	340	
				Reqd: 25.8	4.5		4.0	19,600 w.sh	75
							37,030	17500	
							28,170	1800	
							22,230 sh	340	
4. [UO ₂ (Ace-tol) ₂] HAcc-tol	Orange	180	25	Found: 28.5	4.8	—	19,610 w. sh	70	
				Reqd: 28.3	5.0		37,000	17,000†	
							28,170	1800	
							22,220 sh	340	
						19,600 w. sh	75		

†Whereas the corresponding acetylacetonato complex is the type [UO₂(acac)₂] (dimeric), uranyl acetoacetarylarnides crystallise with one molecule of the ligand. Repeated recrystallisation always resulted 1:3 complex.

Where HAcc-anil=acetoacetanilide; HAcc-Cl-anil=acetoacet-ortho-chloroanilide;
HAcc-anis=acetoacet-o-anisidide; HAcc-tol=acetoacet-o-toluidide.
sh=shoulder; w.sh=weak shoulder.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

**By loss at 110°.

†This high absorption value is due to some contribution of the ligand.

General method of Synthesis of Uranyl Complexes: Uranylacetate dihydrate (0.002 mole) and the appropriate ligand (0.006 mole) were dissolved separately in minimum amount of methanol. These two solutions were then mixed and filtered. The resulting orange red solution was allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature to about half the original volume. The red to orange crystals formed were suction filtered, washed three to four times with ethanol and dried in air. In some cases where an oil was formed, crystalline products were obtained by scratching the oily mass with methanol.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The electrolytic conductance measurements of the complexes in freshly prepared methanol solution indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Where as the conductance values for uni-univalent electrolytes are 90-110 mhos, the values around 20 mhos were observed. But when uranylacetoacetarylamide was added to conductivity water at room temperature, the conductivity rose as the crystals dissolved and then fell rapidly. After about half an hour the solution was opalescent and in a few hours a yellow precipitate of $\text{UO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was formed. (Found: U, 73.5%. Reqd: U, 73.8%). The pH of these solutions were measured and found to be greater than four. As uranyl complexes are known to be extensively hydrolysed in solutions¹¹ of $\text{pH} > 3$, the net reaction at room temperature is probably :

The methanol solution of the complexes also turned opaque after few hours presumably due to the formation of solvent associated species.

The persistence of the uranium-oxygen bond in all the complexes may be considered to be established from the infra-red spectra of the compounds. Uranyl acetoacetarylamides exhibit one strong band around $900\text{-}910 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, characteristic of asymmetric stretching frequency of the uranyl ion. This vibration has been observed in many uranyl complexes^{12,13} in the range $910\text{-}950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, typically around 920 cm^{-1} . All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic as expected for a $5f^0$ system and no major difference between the magnetic properties of the uranyl ions was noticed in these complexes.

Among the most investigated of all the molecular spectra, the electronic spectra of the uranyl compounds have been studied in great detail^{14,15}. The results reveal that the spectra of uranyl complexes are temperature dependent due to the vibronic mixing of excited states and to the coupling of various low frequency molecular and lattice vibrations. Visible and ultraviolet spectra of solutions of uranyl acetoacetarylamides in ethanol

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at 31° exhibit bands around $37,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $28,170\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $22,220\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $19,610\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The appearance of the low intensity bands around $22,220\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $19,610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are typically of O-U-O symmetric stretch frequency for the first excited state. Spectral characteristics of these complexes closely resemble with those of uranyl β -diketones^{13,16-18}. Recently Belford et al¹⁹ have observed resolution in the spectra of crystals of uranyl acetylacetonate. They observed bands around $20,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $19,420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $18,690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and presumed a symmetric dimer form of $\text{UO}_2\text{ acac}_2$. In the present case solid state spectra might have given some indication of resolution in the spectra of these complexes. When ethanolic solutions of uranyl acetoacetarylammides were kept on the light path of a ultraviolet light, no sign of fluorescence was observed at room temperature.

Infra-red spectra support the seven coordination in these complexes. Acetoacetarylammides exhibit two strong bands in the $1650\text{-}1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region due to the acetyl and anilide carbonyl vibrations. Cu(II) and Fe(III) acetoacetarylammides do not show any band in this region due to the replacement of normal carbonyl vibrations by metal chelated carbonyl absorptions at much lower frequencies. But the uranyl acetoacetarylammides exhibit a medium intense band around 1700 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the free acetyl carbonyl of the additional molecule of the ligand. Absence of free anilide carbonyl band points to its coordination with uranium. Thermogravimetric studies reveal that the third molecule of the ligand is lost between $180\text{-}280^\circ\text{C}$ in a single sharp step, and is weakly held than the other two.

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